

A Study of Impulsive Behavior of Adolescents in Bareilly district

Dr. Sonika Choudhary, Associate Professor, Department of Home Science,
Raghunath Girls PG college, Meerut

Lata Gangwar, Research Scholar,
Department of Home Science, Raghunath Girls PG college, Meerut

Abstract

Presented research aimed to study the impulsive behavior of adolescents of Bareilly district on the basis of different gender, boards, localities and streams. For the study null hypotheses was formulated. Descriptive Survey method was used. There was final sample 886 adolescents selected by multistage random sampling method. For data collection Impulsiveness scale (IS) developed by Dr. S. N. Rai & Dr. Alka Sharma The data was analyzed by using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Mean, SD, 't' test and product moment correlation (r). The study revealed that among 16 groups of adolescents belong to different locality, board, gender & streams the urban CBSE board male adolescents of arts stream (UCbMA) were found to be most impulsive in behavior while the Rural CBSE Board Female adolescents of Arts stream (RCbFA) were found to be least impulsive in behavior. Two groups of adolescents of different locality – urban and rural were found to be with significant mean difference. Mean score of urban adolescents was found higher than their rural counterparts. Between two groups of adolescents of different streams, mean score of art stream adolescents was scored higher than their science stream counterparts. But, at the level of significance the mean difference between these two groups is found to be insignificant. Between two groups of adolescents of different gender, mean score of male adolescents was found significantly higher than their female counterparts which indicates that rate of impulsivity among male adolescents is higher than their female counterparts. Significance of mean difference between these two groups is also found to be high. Adolescents of different board i.e. UP and CBSE, were found to be with significant mean difference.

Introduction

Impulsivity includes an immediate and unplanned action (behaviour) that takes place while there has not been enough chance for evaluating the consequences. According to this feature, impulsive behaviour is distinguished from impaired judgment or compulsive behavior in which planning has already taken place before the action.

The fast-paced and competitive world today has changed the person's view of various things. Finally, it reflects the thoughts and behaviour of adolescents. Today they are confident and adopted in a changing environment. Of course, this change is positive and negative both. The way they express themselves in this rapidly changing environment can be look arrogant

In this challenging phase of life, adolescents tend to be unhealthy in their thoughts and habits. Also, physical changes caused in the body attract the opposite sex. It must note that these young teenagers not only waste their energy and efforts on unwanted actions but make mistakes also that cause them to experience depression later on.

From different perspectives of personality theory, impulsiveness has been identified as a personality trait (Barratt, 1965). A number of factor analytic studies have demonstrated the multi-faceted characteristics of impulsiveness as a personality trait.

In an early study, made by Twain (1957) suggested four factors that reflect impulsiveness. These are---

- flexible motor control (erratic motor behaviour in laboratory tests),
- positive progressiveness (Happy-go-lucky),
- action oriented on self-rating scale i.e, aggressive instability (Aggressive and negative on self-rating scales) and
- tenacious self-control (lack of persistence in laboratory tests).

In order to account for the positive aspects of impulsivity, Dickman, S (1990) distinguished between functional impulsivity and dysfunctional impulsivity. Dysfunctional impulsivity is present in several psychiatric disorders that bring about risky behaviors, including bipolar disorder, eating disorders, personality disorders, drug addiction, and ADHD.

To a degree, this kind of behavior is common, especially in children or teenagers, and isn't necessarily a sign of trouble. It's typical for them to act impulsively because their brains are still developing. But in some cases, it can be a part of certain conditions.

Need and Significance of the Study

Adolescence is a shorter period but has a long-term impact on one's life. This stage is a significant period in terms of changes and physical and mental effects in 12 to 18 years. At age, growth is inherent and must be realized by children at that age.

If education has to play a role beyond mere information relocation and certification, a rejuvenation of the system with a drive towards quality is the need of the hour. Consistent and conjunctive efforts addressed at the immense education system are vital not only to encourage optimum performance but also to insure little products capable of independent, analytical linking and enthused for constructive creativity based achievement.

Studies on this subject in western Uttar Pradesh or Rohilkhand region have been negligible, as the researcher found out in the survey of related literature. It becomes necessary to get answers to many questions, such as through the present research it can be understood that what are the causes of impulsive behavior in adolescent boys and girls in Bareilly district. Present study was also necessary from the point of view that impulsivity should be understood as a cause or result of academic achievement because the behavior of adolescent students with low academic achievement will be impulsive, it is considered a universal phenomenon but what is the situation in the context of Bareilly district

Objectives of the Study -The objective of the study was to compare the status of impulsive behavior or impulsivity of adolescents of Bareilly district on the basis of different gender, boards, localities and streams.

Hypothesis of the study-There is no significant difference in status of impulsive behavior or impulsivity of adolescents of Bareilly district on the basis of different gender, boards, localities and streams.

Delimitation of the study- This study was delimited to adolescent students of Bareilly District only.

Design of the study- The research design stands for advance planning of the technique of drawing the adequate and reliable sample, tools to be used for collecting the necessary data. The Descriptive Survey method has been used as it is the most appropriate one according to the objectives and nature of study. In the present study, the multi-stage random sampling technique has been adopted. In the present research, the sample size selected is that of 886 adolescents. For data collection, the tool that has been selected is the impulsiveness scale developed and standardized by Dr. S.N. RAI & Dr. Alka Sharma. The statistical techniques which have been used are Mean, SD, ANOVA and 't'- test.

Result and Discussion –**Table No-1**

Mean and SD scores of adolescents of 16 (2x2x2x2) groups belongs to different locality,board, gender & streams on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable

<i>Groups</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
Urban UP Board Male Arts (UUpMA)	58	17.48	4.57
Urban UP Board Male Science (UUpMS)	52	17.67	4.38
Urban CBSE Board Male Arts(UCbMA)	46	21.11	4.58
Urban CBSE Board Male Science (UCMS)	56	16.14	3.58
Urban UP Board Female Arts (UUpFA)	57	16.63	3.66
Urban UP Board Female Science (UUpFS)	52	14.88	3.58
Urban CBSE Board Female Arts (UCbFA)	64	16.78	3.45
Urban CBSE Board Female Science (UCbFS)	21	12.62	2.85
Rural UP Board Male Arts (RUpMA)	64	13.23	2.04
Rural UP Board Male Science (RUpMS)	68	16.04	2.29
Rural CBSE Board Male Arts (RCbMA)	65	16.17	3.22
Rural CBSE Board Male Science(RCbMS)	59	17.80	4.54
Rural UP Board Female Arts (RUpFA)	81	12.68	3.58
Rural UP Board Female Science (RUpFS)	79	12.91	3.33
Rural CBSE Board Female Arts (RCbFA)	41	10.37	2.05
Rural CBSE Board Female Science (RCbFS)	23	11.91	2.95

Table 1 shows the mean and SD values of each group of adolescents belong to different locality, board, gender & streams on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable . Data reveal that among 16 groups , the highest mean and SD (M=21.11, SD= 4.58) was scored by Urban CBSE board male adolescents of arts stream (UCbMA) while the lowest mean and SD (M=10.37, SD= 2.05) value was scored by Rural CBSE Board Female adolescents of Arts stream (RCbFA). This indicates that Urban CBSE board male adolescents of arts stream (UCbMA) were found to be most impulsive in behavior while the Rural CBSE Board Female adolescents of Arts stream (RCbFA) were found to be least impulsive in behavior.

Table No-2

Variance among scores of adolescents of 16 (2x2x2x2) groups belongs to different locality,board, gender & streams on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F-Value</i>
Between Groups	5548.33	15	369.90	29.63**
Within Groups	10862.12	870	12.49	
Total	16410.46	885		

** *significant at 0.01 level*

Table 2 shows the variance among scores of adolescents of 16 (2x2x2x2) groups belongs to different locality, board, gender & streams on Impulsive Scale (IS) . As the calculated value of variance (F=29.63, p= 0,01) found very high at 870 df ,it indicates that mean difference among these 16 groups is highly significant. On the basis of this it can be said that ,in reference to impulsivity , locality, board, gender & streams of the adolescents play

significant role .there fore the first hypothesis stated –“• **There is no significant difference in status of impulsive behavior or impulsivity of adolescents of Bareilly district on the basis of different gender, boards, localities and streams**” may be rejected.

Table No-3

Significance of mean difference between scores of adolescents of 2 groups belongs to different localities on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable

Urban			Rural			df	t-Value
N ₁	M ₁	σ_1	N ₂	M ₂	σ_2		
406	16.92	4.34	480	14.14	3.84	884	10.12**

** *significant at 0.01 level*

In the Table 3 mean and SD scores of two groups of adolescents of different locality are presented

. Data revealed that mean score of urban adolescents is higher than their rural counterparts ($M_1 > M_2$) which indicates that rate of impulsivity among urban students is higher than adolescents of rural background. Significance of mean difference between these two groups is also found to be high ($t = 10.12$, $p = 0.01$) at 884 df ,which denotes that urban students are significantly more impulsive than rural adolescents .

Table No-4

Significance of mean difference between scores of adolescents of 2 groups belongs to different streams on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable

Arts			Science			df	t-Value
N ₁	M ₁	σ_1	N ₂	M ₂	σ_2		
476	15.46	4.52	410	15.36	4.06	884	0.34ns

In the Table 4. ,mean and SD scores of two groups of adolescents of different streams are presented

. Data revealed that mean score of art stream adolescents is higher than their science stream counterparts ($M_1 > M_2$) which indicates that rate of impulsivity among art stream students is higher than adolescents of science stream . but at the level of significance the mean difference between these two groups is found to be insignificant at both level ($t = 0.34$, ns) at 884 df ,which denotes that rate of impulsivity among science and art stream adolescents is almost similar .In this situation the first hypothesis may be partially accepted .

Table No-5

Significance of mean difference between scores of adolescents of 2 groups belongs to different gender on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable

Male			Female			df	t-Value
N ₁	M ₁	σ_1	N ₂	M ₂	σ_2		
468	16.77	4.18	418	13.89	3.91	884	10.52**

** *significant at 0.01 level*

In the Table 5, ,mean and SD scores of two groups of adolescents of different gender are presented

. Data revealed that mean score of male adolescents is higher than their female counterparts ($M_1 > M_2$) which indicates that rate of impulsivity among male adolescents is higher than their female counterparts. Significance of mean difference between these two groups is also found to be high ($t = 10.52$, $p = 0.01$) at 884 df ,which denotes that

male students are significantly more impulsive than female adolescents. Generally, female adolescents are more cool and calm.

Table No-6

Significance of mean difference between scores of adolescents of 2 groups belongs to different boards on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable

Up Board			CBSE Board			df	t-Value
N ₁	M ₁	σ_1	N ₂	M ₂	σ_2		
511	14.95	3.96	375	21.76	4.66	884	3.74**

** *significant at 0.01 level*

In the Table 6, mean and SD scores of two groups of adolescents of different board are presented

. Data revealed that mean score of CBSE Board adolescents is higher than their UP board counterparts ($M_2 > M_1$) which indicates that rate of impulsivity among CBSE Board students is higher than adolescents of UP board. Significance of mean difference between these two groups is also found to be high ($t = 3.74$, $p = 0.01$) at 884 df, which denotes that CBSE board students are significantly more impulsive than UP board adolescents.

Conclusion -

After the analysis and interpretation of data, it is important to reach the conclusions based on findings. Therefore, researcher mentioned the major findings as follows-

- Among 16 groups of adolescents belong to different locality, board, gender & streams on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable. The urban CBSE board male adolescents of arts stream (UCbMA) were found to be most impulsive in behavior while the Rural CBSE Board Female adolescents of Arts stream (RCbFA) were found to be least impulsive in behavior.
- Mean difference among these above 16 groups was highly significant..
- Two groups of adolescents of different locality – urban and rural on Impulsive Scale (IS) variable were found to be with significant mean difference. Mean score of urban adolescents was found higher than their rural counterparts which indicates that rate of impulsivity among urban students is higher than adolescents of rural background.
- Between two groups of adolescents of different streams, mean score of art stream adolescents was scored higher than their science stream counterparts. But, at the level of significance the mean difference between these two groups is found to be insignificant which denotes that rate of impulsivity among science and art stream adolescents is almost similar
- Between two groups of adolescents of different gender, mean score of male adolescents was found significantly higher than their female counterparts which indicates that rate of impulsivity among male adolescents is higher than their female counterparts. Significance of mean difference between these two groups is also found to be high, which denotes that male students are significantly more impulsive than female adolescents. Generally, female adolescents are more cool and calm.
- Adolescents of different board i.e. UP and CBSE, were found to be with significant mean difference. Through, mean score of CBSE Board adolescents was found higher than their

UP board counterparts which indicates that rate of impulsivity among CBSE Board students is higher than adolescents of UP board .

Implications

Policy makers and educationists need to develop new ways to improve social behavior among these students. This can be done through ongoing counseling programs, seminars, role playing in plays, etc. This will, in the long run, help students for enhancing academic achievement and developing a productive and mature member of society. Based on the findings obtained from the study, the following educational implications can be drawn:

- The present study is helpful in guiding and modifying the effect of impulsivity by teachers at the school level and parents at the family level.
- This study is able to identify and overcome the problems arising in daily classroom teaching due to impulsive behavior of the child.
- It is also suggest to create an environment to reduce impulsiveness among boys specially.
- This study suggests that impulsivity requires multiple treatments. A combination of educational behavioral interventions can help adolescents be successful at home and at school. This treatment requires teamwork and shared responsibility for the school's success

.The parents, care taker, health care professional, school teachers, administrators, special teachers, and the school itself can work together to design psychologically effective intervention plans that address individual weaknesses and build on strengths. .

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